

Faculty of Clinical Informatics Accreditation Scheme and Process

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Faculty of Clinical Informatics Accreditation Scheme and Process

Guidance for Learning Providers

This document will outline the process for accrediting an education and training activity or individual against the Core Competency Framework (CCF) for the Faculty of Clinical Informatics (FCI).

Background

The FCI Core Competencies Project (CCP) has been designed to achieve two aims:

1. Develop professional competencies for clinical informaticians.
2. Provide a process for FCI accreditation of training and education programmes and individuals

These two aims have been fulfilled through three main phases of work:

Phase 1: To develop, test and define the output core competences required of a professional clinical informatician; and

Phase 2: To define the core skills, knowledge and traits that constitute the core (input) competencies¹ to enable an individual to do the job.

Phase 3: To develop a process and define the evidence required for FCI training programme accreditation.

The two main outputs of phases 1 and 2 can also be found at the [FCI website](#). Phase 3 builds on these to devise a process that will be able to accredit education and training for the FCI.

This document outlines both the process and types of evidence required to be able to accredit education and training that will provide all or some of the necessary knowledge and skills for an individual clinical informatician (CI) to use as part of their professional education, training and personal development. Demonstration that an individual has achieved the standards set out in the Competency Framework (CF) should enable that person to satisfy the membership criteria for the FCI.

Accreditation enables the education deliverer to seek permission to use the Faculty of Clinical Informatics logo on education/training documentation and certificates and any marketing materials including web-pages for only the education and training that has met the parts of the core competency framework. The module or programme will also be listed on the FCI website as accredited education/training with brief details of the competencies that it meets.

For an individual, demonstration of meeting the core competencies will allow you to apply to become a member of the professional body of clinical informaticians.

Clinical Informatics Definition

Clinical informatics has been defined by the community as ***'the application of data and information technology to improve patient and population health, care and wellbeing outcomes and to advance treatment and the delivery of personalised, coordinated support from health and social care.'***

¹ 'Core' in this context denotes the minimum knowledge base that all CIs must have to be eligible to become members of the FCI and excludes further sub-specialist avenues of education.

To be able to work in the field a clinical informatician ***“uses their clinical knowledge and experience of informatics concepts, methods and tools to promote patient and population care that is person-centred, ethical, safe, effective, efficient, timely, and equitable.”***

Clinical informaticians can work across a wider range of settings in health and social care including the NHS, social care, private healthcare providers, universities, or by organisations providing informatics solutions.

It is a dynamic field with a developing knowledge base and with a demonstrable demand of suitably accredited professionals. This accreditation scheme supports this by recognising education and training that develops the knowledge and skills to be able to work as a clinical informatician, and develops a professional body of evidence for clinical informaticians that sets the standard for those working in the field.

To be eligible as a member or fellow of the FCI a clinical informatician must be a registered health or care professional registered with one of the regulators overseen by the Professional Standards Authority. In addition, an individual must also be able to demonstrate that they can meet all the FCI core competencies as defined by CCF.

Faculty of Clinical Informatics Accreditation Scheme

The FCI, as the professional body for clinical informaticians, can accredit education and training, as well as individuals.

Clinical (Health) informatics programmes, courses and modules that are relevant to healthcare can be accredited if they map onto the core competencies outlined in supporting documents and on the website: <https://facultyofclinicalinformatics.org.uk/core-competency-framework>.

If a programme can meet all of these competencies, then it is sufficient for an individual who has studied on the programme, and is also a registered health or care professional registered with one of the regulators overseen by the Professional Standards Authority, to apply to become a member of the FCI.

However, it may not always be possible for a programme to meet all requirements, thus it is possible to accredit modules or short courses against a subsection of the CCF. This will not entitle an individual who has studied the module becoming a full member of the FCI, but this can be used as evidence by that individual towards membership of the FCI. In other words, it is possible to become a member of the FCI if an individual has completed a number of different modules or courses (accredited by the FCI) that in their totality map onto all of the core competencies defined by the FCI. In this latter case, the individual would need to provide evidence of modules or programmes completed as well as any other work-based evidence that would support their application to becoming a member.

Details of the accreditation process for education providers and for individuals are outlined below.

Benefits to Education and Training Accreditation

There are a number of benefits associated with accreditation of programmes and individuals, but overall it shows a commitment to the provision of a continuous high quality learning environment to meet the needs of clinical informaticians.

Award: Individuals who have successfully completed the education/training will be able to apply for membership of the FCI.

Recruitment onto programme: Individuals looking to complete and meet the competencies will be drawn to the accredited education/training. Education providers will also be able to apply to use the FCI logo on relevant course materials, and the module/programme accredited will be listed on the FCI website.

Employability: In a field that is rapidly evolving and requires greater numbers of informaticians, individuals who study on accredited programme are likely to have good employment prospects, which is attractive to future applicants and students.

Design of Programmes: any future programmes can be designed using the CCF, and acquire accreditation from the FCI.

For Health and Social Care Organisations and Individuals

Professionalism: Contribute to the current work and promotion of the clinical informatics workforce through raising the profile and identity of this group within the wider health and social care workforce.

Workforce Capability: There is demonstrated demand of **informatics skills** for clinicians and through having accredited education it secures a continuous availability of high quality relevant learning opportunities.

Capacity: There is a need to increase the number of skilled individuals in clinical informatics to match the vision of the health and social care sector. Accreditation also raises this profile and encourages new clinicians into the field.

Programme & Module Eligibility

This accreditation focusses on education and training provided by all providers across sectors including: Higher Education Institutions (HEIs); Further Education Institutions (FEIs), and both NHS and commercial educational providers. It focusses on awarding accreditation to module, course or programme levels, and when it has been demonstrated that the competencies have been successfully mapped, the provider can apply to use the logo of the FCI in conjunction with the education and training. It must be noted, that in instances where parts of programmes have been successfully mapped, then the logo can only be used alongside that element of the programme. There are two main types of course structure that can be accredited:

<u>Structure</u>	<u>Description</u>
Module/Unit/Course	This is a distinct unit of study or training that focusses on a specific theme. This will be anything less than 300 total learning hours ² , which includes timetabled and non-timetabled activities ³ . In some cases modules can be part of a wider programme such as nursing or medical undergraduate degrees: these can be recognised as stand-alone modules that are independent of the

² Modules are often in 10, 15, 20 or 30 credit format at HEIs.

³ This figure has been based on maximum number of credits attributed to a module of study across education providers. 1 credit in HE is equivalent to 10 learning hours in accordance with the Credit Framework (QAA).

	other elements of the programme of study.
Programme	This is a collection of units/modules that define a broader scheme of study or training, and often results in a recognised qualification, such as a PGCert, PGDip or MSc.

Both will have a set of defined aims and learning objectives and will be delivered via a set of activities.

Accreditation Criteria and Process

To accredit education and training, the learning provider must complete the two sections in the CCP accreditation workbook (Appendix A⁴): (1) education/training content and assessment through mapping to the FCI Core Competencies, and (2) general information about the education/training being accredited. Further information on how to complete these is provided below.

(1) Education/Training Content and Assessment

In the six tables (outlined in the workbook) that each represent a domain in the CCF, please identify the specific aims, learning outcomes, assessments or activities that best map to core competencies (a list of examples evidence is supplied below). If it isn't clear how the outcome is achieved or assessed then please provide additional details. It is recognised that there may not be a one to one relationship between the competencies and the learning outcomes, and that some competencies could map to one learning outcome, and vice versa. When it is not clear, please do provide a brief explanation how the objective and competency map.

(2) Programme Information

In the 'Additional Information' tab of the spreadsheet, please provide details about the education and training you wish to accredit. This includes the programme/module name, qualification (if appropriate) as well as details of those delivering the materials. Where appropriate, additional information such as CVs, can be provided.

Sources of Evidence for Programme/Module Accreditation and Mapping

The table below outlines the various evidence types that can be used to accredit education or training. One or a combination of these can be used to map across to a core competency, or provision of general information.

<u>Evidence Type</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Examples</u>
Aims	This is a statement of intent that specifies the desired outcome that is usually written in broad terms. These are useful especially for competencies that are focussed on 'transferable or personal' skills such as communication.	Aim: Provide learners with the skills required to manage healthcare systems in the rapidly changing health economy.
Learning Objectives (LOs)	Brief statements that are clear and measurable of what learners will be able to do at the end of	LO1: Understand the flow of data/information and

⁴ Faculty of Clinical Informatics Accreditation Mapping Education Providers.docx

	the lesson as a result of a set of activities. They are often defined in categories: Knowledge and Understanding; Intellectual Skills (<i>i.e.</i> , application of knowledge); Practical Skills; and Professional Skills and Personal Qualities/Behaviours.	knowledge and its use across the health and social care system, or LO2: Evaluate a system, product or service from a defined perspective e.g. assuring that stakeholder requirements have been met.
Assessment	A piece of work or activity that is set to be able to test whether an individual has met the learning objectives. Assessments can come in two main forms: formative, which monitors learners understanding and provides ongoing feedback that can help learners, whereas summative assessment evaluates learning at the end of instruction by comparing it against a benchmark. Both are relevant for the accreditation.	Summative: Be presented with a set of requirements for an information system and critically appraise whether a proposal has met these. Formative: discussion group sharing experiences of a successful or poor evaluation of an information system.
Activities	Educational activities are any type of activity that is designed to impart knowledge or skill. These can be in many forms including lectures, workshops, problem-based group learning, structured tutorial programme, discussions, student-led projects, online activities.	Stakeholder requirements gathering of five different roles for the development of an information system. These are to be conducted and recorded in a formal and professional manner.
Additional or Supporting Documentation	Additional or supporting documentation can be provided with the mapping and programme information workbook to support statements or provide more detail or context around the submitted information.	FCI Registration number of tutors CVs of tutors Programme or Module Handbook Website link to programme/module information

Individual Eligibility

An individual can also apply for accreditation to the Faculty of Clinical Informatics through providing evidence and information for each core competency. The individual must also be a health or care professional registered with one of the regulators overseen by the Professional Standards Authority.

For an individual to apply they are required to fill out the two sheets in the 'Individual Accreditation' workbook (Appendix B): (1) provision of information/evidence to show how the competency has been met; and (2) personal information. Both of these are required for the application to be considered. Details of the process are discussed below.

(1) Competency Evidence

The FCI 'Individual Accreditation' workbook (Appendix B) for individual accreditation has six tables (each representing a different domain in the CCF) that outlines the core competencies for clinical informaticians. For each competency, evidence is required to show that you have met it. Evidence types (see below) are varied but we would anticipate that these will be gained through attendance on educational programmes/training or through the workplace.

Evidence provided for each competency must be clear and concise, and relevant to the competency. It need not be a one-off activity that meets the competency, but can also be a task that is repeated over time and your reflections about the completion each time. Completion of a competency is not about it being the 'best it can be', but about showing that it has been significantly attempted, supported by a statement of how you might do things differently. It isn't necessary to write an extensive piece, but nor should you just list of your knowledge, it is much easier to show how you have applied it in your context. Think differently how you might evidence meeting the competency - a video, blog or colleagues supporting statement are also suitable (dependent on the competency). Below is a list of examples of evidence and how they might be used against the framework.

(2) Personal Information

The second form focusses on personal information, qualifications to date and professional membership. Please also attach your CV, and ask a sponsor for a supporting statement for your application and the meeting of the competencies.

Sources of Evidence for Individual Accreditation and Mapping

There are a number sources of evidence that an individual can use to prove that they have met all core competencies, and the table below shows a list of them and how they can be used.

<u>Evidence Type</u>	<u>Evidence to provide</u>
Attendance at training events and conferences that are accredited against the FCI framework.	Certificate of completion and brief details of course
Attendance at training events or educational programmes such as university programmes	Certificate of course, brief details of course
Presentations/Reports	Presentation details, brief summary and narrative of presentation, and how the competency was demonstrated to be met through it
Minutes of a meeting where the applicant is shown to have contributed significantly	The highlighted minutes with a brief explanation of your contribution
Case-studies or discussions	Details of the case-study, outcome and where you would do things differently, or an explanation on how the competency was required to deliver the work.
Podcasts/Videos	These could be used when discussing and explaining a topic to someone else. Details of this and how the competency was used.
Work-based projects/programmes	Details of projects/programmes, your involvement and a colleagues short supporting statement.

Summary of Application Process

The application process for accreditation of education/training and individuals is very similar; the difference is that educational providers map their programme across the competencies, whereas individuals provide evidence from training and workplace to demonstrate they have those competencies. Step 1 of the process refers to different documents for these two instances, but after completion the review process is the same for both forms of accreditation.

Step 1: Submission of Core Competency Mapping

For an Educational Provider

The educational provider must complete both pages in the FCI Education Provider Accreditation workbook (Appendix A). The programme information tab, must be filled out once for an entire programme, or completed separately for each module submitted for accreditation. If your programme does not meet all the core competencies, then it is critical that you fill out form for each of the individual modules that meet competencies.

You can seek accreditation at any time – either in the development phase or delivery. All applications must be authorised by the programme director or manager, or other appropriate learning officer at the institution.

For an Individual

An individual must complete both pages in the FCI Individual Accreditation workbook (Appendix B). You can seek accreditation any time, but please note in order to become a member of the FCI you will need to have met **all** the core competencies as well as be a member of a professional body.

Step 2: Accreditation Review Panel

Once the application has been received this will be reviewed by an FCI panel who will be able to advise whether the application has been successful.

Step 3: Notification of Results

If an application is **successful** then the applicant will be notified and will be set a date of review (usually two years). For education providers, the education/training details will be submitted on the FCI website. For individuals, membership to the FCI will be confirmed.

If an application is **not successful** then the applicant will be asked to resolve the issues. The review panel will provide a short explanation about why the application has failed and the applicant will be able to resubmit (as above) once issues have been resolved.

For education providers: accreditation will normally last two years, unless otherwise specified or there is substantial revision of the content, which the FCI would strongly advise you to resubmit for accreditation.

Accreditation and the use of the FCI logo will be tied to a specific date / version of the course or programme material and to an evidence portfolio to support membership application.

Checklist for Education/Training Accreditation

On the application for accreditation of education and training, please ensure you have completed the following sections and email to <insert email address>.

Completed:

FCI Education Accreditation Spreadsheet including:	<u>Completed (Y/N)</u>
(1) Programme Information	
(2) Confirmation of all aims, LOs, assessment and activities that are mapped to the FCI CCF	
Additional documentation that supports information provided in the spreadsheet (e.g., CVs, programme or module handbooks).	

Checklist for Individual Accreditation

On the application for an individual accreditation, please ensure you have completed the following sections and email to <insert email address>.

FCI Individual Accreditation Workbook including:	<u>Completed (Y/N)</u>
(1) Personal Information	
(2) Confirmation that all core competencies have supporting documentation	
Additional documentation that supports information provided in the workbook (e.g., CV, professional registration number, sponsor supporting statement)	